

Callaghan Innovation Report 1088

The FAIR principle interoperability and representation of measured quantities

Blair D. Hall

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Measurement Standards Laboratory of New Zealand
Lower Hutt, New Zealand

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Summary

This document has been prepared prior to the establishment of a new cross-sectional CIPM *Forum for Metrology and Digitalization*. It draws on the experience of an expert group that has been supporting the CIPM Task Group on the Digital SI ([CIPM-TG-DIG](#)). However, the opinions expressed here are not necessarily shared by all members of that group.

The report has two sections. The first discusses the third FAIR principle, ‘interoperability’, and the importance of semantic models to make sense of interoperable data. The second section discusses the conventional scientific notation for units, and points out some difficulties with interpretation.

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1 Interoperability

1.1 FAIR principles

By facilitating sharing and reuse of scientific data,¹ the FAIR principles are believed to increase the impact of scientific activities and the value derived from them [Wilkinson et al., 2016]. Adoption of the principles is just beginning within metrology communities, but there is no shortage of guidance available about the FAIR principles and how to apply them to scientific data management.

The abbreviation FAIR stands for: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The three principles findable, accessible, and reusable apply to metrological data in much the same way as they do to data in other scientific disciplines. However, interoperability seems to be a more challenging principle for metrology.

To engage with the broad community of stakeholders in the SI, regarding digitalisation of the International System of Units (SI), a workshop entitled *The SI in FAIR Digital Data* was organised in 2021.² Some participants at the workshop expressed a strong opinion that metrological traceability should be considered a new fifth principle; that is, FAIR should be extended to FAIR+T. However, the FAIR principles are domain independent.³ So, it is actually a task for metrology communities to reach an agreement on how metrologically traceable data can be made FAIR.

1.2 Interoperability

In the context of digital systems, there are two types of interoperability: syntactic and semantic. The ‘I’ in FAIR refers to syntactic interoperability. Syntactic interoperability is the ability of different systems to exchange data without transmission errors, which can usually be achieved by defining data formats and protocols. FAIR data should be accessible in a form that allows different systems and tools to use it correctly.

Semantic interoperability is achieved when the meaning attributed to some data is preserved, without human intervention, as the data passes from one system to another. This type of interoperability gives systems the potential to act more autonomously.

Semantics are always an important consideration for interoperability. When syntactic interoperability is provided, people with an understanding of what the data means must supervise the generation and use of data, or develop appropriate automatic processes that produce and consume it. Usually different groups of people are involved, so it is important to establish a common understanding of the semantics in order to use data correctly.

1.3 An example

It is difficult to perceive any meaning in the sequence of digits shown in figure 1. Nevertheless, knowing that the data is a stream of hexadecimal characters, syntactic interoperability (in the sense of lossless exchange of data) may be provided.

Figure 2 presents the same data, but now shown as ASCII characters. It appears more meaningful. However, we still lack a context in which to make sense of it.

¹Broadly speaking, *data* here can apply to any digital record created by (scientific) metrological activities. This includes information generated by measurement, as well as other digital documents, audio and video recordings, etc.

²<https://www.bipm.org/en/bipm-workshops/digital-si>

³Extension of the abbreviation FAIR with additional letters is contrary to guidance on implementing the principles (see step 1 in Hodson et al. [2018]).

0A202020202231312025222C0A20202020
22636F6C20647520476C616E646F6E222C
0A202020202232206B6D222C0A20202020
2231373130206D220A

Figure 1: A sequence of hexadecimal digits.

"11 %",
"col du Glandon",
"2 km",
"1710 m"

Figure 2: The hexadecimal digits in figure 1 correspond to these ASCII characters.

Hopefully, readers find figure 3 meaningful. From this image, we understand that “1710 m” is the altitude at the location of the milestone in the image and that “11 %” is a measure of the gradient, over the next “2 km”, to the “*Col du Glandon*”, further on up the road (indicated by the upward arrow head).

The image helps people to understand the data. The details become almost self-explanatory. So, the milestone facilitates semantic interoperability for people.

Figure 3: The inscriptions on this milestone correspond to the text in figure 2.

1.4 Meaning

Semantic interoperability is not easily achieved. If we knew nothing about milestones, the milestone image loses its effect: the image would not bring to mind our knowledge needed to understand the inscription. However, hopefully the image triggers recall of ideas about milestones and geographical information. These contextual ideas provide a sense of meaning about the location, the steepness of roads, height above sea level, etc.

Understanding relationships between symbols, concepts, and actual things is fundamental, but easily overlooked. Figure 4, from the influential work on semantics and linguistics by [Ogden and Richards \[1923\]](#), shows the relations schematically. No line is drawn across the base of the triangle, because there is no direct relation between symbols and the things they refer to.

Figure 4: This figure shows the indirect relationship between a symbol (lower left vertex) and what is referred to by the symbol (lower right vertex) [Ogden and Richards, 1923]. We are often unaware of the intermediate step (top vertex) that is needed to make sense of symbols. For instance, the word (symbol) 'dog' becomes associated with an actual dog (referent) by drawing on our thoughts about dogs.

Meaning is obtained indirectly, from the relationships between symbols, thoughts, and things in the world.

This way of de-constructing thought processes is unfamiliar to most of us. However, we need to be aware of the role played by intuitive ideas. Nothing is intuitive to a digital system!

Contextual information is not always easy to capture. In this example, even if we were to label data with textual keys (perhaps producing the JSON object shown in figure 5, which a person would find helpful), we would not have captured any semantics for machines: a system receiving such data still needs to associate the keys with relationships that exist between them (not to mention how to interpret the quantity-value data). People will say that they understand

```
{
  "type": "milestone",
  "gradient": "11 %",
  "next location": "col du Glandon",
  "distance to location": "2 km",
  "altitude": "1710 m"
}
```

Figure 5: ASCII data can be labelled, as shown here in a JSON object, but this does not convey meaning to another machine.

data if they have an adequate conceptual model in mind, but this needs to be formalised so that a system can relate modelled concepts to the data.⁴

⁴Conceptual models have been developed for geographical data. The book by Hart and Dolbear [2013] is a good introduction to linking data with conceptual models.

1.5 Purpose

In order to achieve interoperability, we need to know why information is needed.

The milestone in figure 3 is not typical. For one thing, it was made recently, whereas milestones have long ceased to be used for signage on highways. The information inscribed is also unusual: milestones do not typically indicate altitude or gradient.

In fact, the data meets the needs of travellers in that region. The route is popular for cycling and cycle racing, so the milestone helps cyclists to understand where they are.

A lot of information about the milestone itself is not shown in figure 3. What is it made of? Who made it and how? Who is responsible for maintaining it? What is the origin of the data inscribed? And so on. To someone tasked with curating milestones, such information would be important. Perhaps it can be accessed using an identifier (e.g., a serial number) discretely out of sight on the milestone. If so, the interoperability of such data would be seen in terms of the different need for information.

1.6 Digitalisation and digital transformation

If asked to carry out a digital transformation of these milestones, how would we approach the task?

Perhaps, if the purpose is to curate local milestones, we would build a database in which the concept of a milestone is represented. If, instead, the purpose is to enhance the experience of road users, then perhaps milestones are no longer even needed. A service to convey geographical information directly to cyclists and other tourists could use portable digital devices with access to global navigation satellite systems.

This illustrates a distinction between digitalisation and digital transformation. Digitalisation is the process of making information available in a convenient digital form. It requires an understanding of how people use the data. So, semantics are important. However, digitalisation need not be transformative; it will usually just provide information in a convenient form.

Digital transformation, on the other hand, will often integrate a number of digitalised features, but the technology being used is often unobtrusive. Transformation produces alternative and, often, ‘better’ services (by hand-held portable navigation devices). Transformation leads to substantial, not incremental, change and may satisfy new requirements as well—portable digital devices may process data for a variety of sources and work in different regions with geographical information stored in different systems, all of which calls for interoperability ([Hart and Dolbear \[2013\]](#) gives more detail).

1.7 Meaning and measures

The milestone presents physical information for people. The gradient is a ratio of different types of length: the difference in height (altitude), between the *Col* and the milestone, is divided by the distance to be travelled between the milestone and the *Col*. The path length of 2 km is presumably along a winding mountain road (rather than a direct point-to-point distance). The altitude is a measure of height above some official point defined as sea level in the region.

To make sense of all this data, an observer must know and understand: the distinction between height (altitude or elevation) and displacement along a path, both of which are lengths; symbols for SI units; knowledge of local geography (place names and locations); and the association between the steepness of a road and cycling. These ideas are not inscribed on the stone.

Furthermore, quantity values are reported in different precisions, and it is not clear how accurate the values are. Indeed, another road sign actually located at the *Col du Glandon* reports the altitude there as 1924 m, whereas a calculation using the inscribed data yields 1930 m. A person would not expect 2 km to be exactly 2000 m in this context, so this discrepancy would probably not come as a surprise. Nevertheless, at face value, the use of just one significant figure implies a rather inaccurate value, which is clearly not the case. A person might reasonably suppose that the local authority would place milestones close to kilometre stages, or add more significant figures if that is not feasible.

2 Quantities, units, etc.

If the semantic models we use to interpret notation for units and physical quantities are not robust, implementations of the FAIR interoperability principle for metrological data could be unnecessarily complicated.

The CIPM Expert Group considered different digital representations for SI units but did not reach a consensus view. The group resolved instead to encourage adoption of best-practice. With that in mind, this section discusses some of the important semantic difficulties associated with unit representation.

2.1 Quantity

The idea of quantities, like mass, length, duration, etc., at the summit of a semantic triangle (Figure 4), can be related to real-world properties of things at the lower right vertex. The general notion of quantity can be tailored to specific quantity kinds by finding physical processes that correspond closely to arithmetic operations (e.g., placing lengths of rod end-to-end to represent addition).⁵ At the left vertex, symbols, like m_1 , m_2 , and Δm , and arithmetic operators, can be related to characteristics of the physical concepts at the summit. In this way ideas expressed using scientific notation (on the left) can be related to meaningful real-world properties (on the right).

The distinctive characteristics of the quantity concept are:

1. a quantity has magnitude;
2. there is an intrinsic zero magnitude for each kind of quantity;
3. quantities of the same kind can be compared by ratio;
4. quantities of the same kind can be compared by difference;
5. quantities of the same kind can be compared by order.

In addition to these characteristics, there is a sense in which individual quantities of the same kind can be combined (added or subtracted) with the result being a quantity of the same kind.⁶ This means that the sense of zero magnitude is somehow equivalent to the sense of zero magnitude difference. For example, when several rods have the same length, the amount of length that must be added to one rod to make it the same length as another is zero. Not all measurable properties interpret zero in this way, so these properties are not strictly speaking

⁵There are no particular difficulties in finding operational equivalents for arithmetic operations for extensive quantities. For intensive quantities, however, it becomes much harder. For example, there are no simple operational interpretations corresponding to the addition of temperatures or densities. However, this issue has been resolved. See §6.3.6 in [Mari et al. \[2023\]](#) for a nice explanation about the quantity temperature.

⁶The way in which addition and subtraction correspond to physical processes depends on the quantity, but a sense for addition is needed to construct a scale. It is possible for the same unit and same intrinsic zero to be associated with different non-linearly related scales [Ellis \[1964\]](#), although this does not seem to arise in practice.

quantities. For example, it is nonsense to think that a temperature difference of $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is equivalent to a temperature of $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponds to the freezing point of water.

2.1.1 Difficulties

These characteristics underpin the arithmetic properties used in quantity equations and therefore in physical modelling. However, there is a broader, colloquial, sense of ‘quantity’ that people may also use. This is the idea of a property that can be quantified without necessarily producing data compatible with the scientific idea of a quantity. We can, for example, say that the (quantity) temperature of a body is hotter or colder than some other reference temperature. In this case, arithmetic operations make no sense (although there would be order relations).

2.2 Units

Designated reference magnitudes (e.g., the kilogram, metre, and second) are used to express quantity magnitudes. For example, when we write 9.8 kg , the symbol “kg” refers to a mass reference called ‘kilogram’, and the numerical factor 9.8 is the ratio of the mass of interest to one kilogram.

It is important to note that two pieces of information are inferred from the unit symbol here: the quantity kind and the quantity reference.

2.2.1 Difficulties

Several problems arise from the idea that unit symbols refer directly to the magnitudes of certain physical quantities.

First, there is a one-to-many relation between unit names and quantity kinds, which means an SI unit name is not a reliable way of identifying a quantity. For instance, $\text{N} \cdot \text{m}$ can be used for energy and torque, and s^{-1} is a unit for frequency and activity. We can see immediately that the idea of a unit name corresponding to an unambiguous reference magnitude is not supported by scientific notation.

Second, not all expressions in the form of a number multiplied by unit make physical sense. One example is temperature expressed in degrees Celsius. A quantity value like $15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ cannot be thought of as a ratio of quantities (the temperature is not 15 times greater than $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The difficulty here is a fixed offset between the scales for Celsius temperature and thermodynamic temperature. Temperature conversion between Celsius and kelvin involves a numerical value equation [BIPM, 2019]

$$t/^{\circ}\text{C} = T/\text{K} - 273.15. \quad (1)$$

This shows that $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \neq 0\text{ K}$, so it would appear that thermodynamic temperature and Celsius temperature are not the same kind of quantity. However, measurement specialists do not consider there to be fundamental differences between temperature expressed in kelvin and temperature expressed in degrees Celsius (for a more detailed description of the problems posed by temperature-related quantities, see Hall et al. [2023]).

Furthermore, it appears that treating Celsius temperature as a quantity is not appropriate in terms of quantity calculus. The SI Brochure introduces Celsius temperature with the quantity equation

$$t = T - T_0, \quad (2)$$

where the lower case t denotes Celsius temperature, and states that the unit degree Celsius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) is equal in size to the unit kelvin (K). However, if Celsius temperature and thermodynamic

temperature are indeed different quantities, then the quantity equation (2) cannot *define* Celsius temperature, because the quantity kind of a difference must be the same as the terms subtracted. This rule of the calculus means that all terms in equation (2) must represent the same kind of quantity, so t must be thought of as a thermodynamic temperature difference, and not a distinct derived quantity.

2.3 Dimensions

To understand why there is not a one-to-one correspondence between SI unit names and quantity kinds, we need to look at the concept of a physical dimension. Dimension represents the idea that different but equivalent expressions of a particular magnitude are possible. A dimension is the class of equivalent units used to express a particular kind of quantity [Ellis, 1964]. For example, the metre, foot, inch, etc., belong to the dimension of length.

2.3.1 Difficulties

Somewhat confusingly, ‘dimension’ is used with a slightly different meaning in unit systems like the SI, which have a particular formal structure. This alternative use of ‘dimension’ may be confusing.

The SI Brochure states that *physical quantities can be organized in a system of dimensions, where the system used is decided by convention* [BIPM, 2019]. This statement relates to the choice of a set of base quantities, with corresponding base dimensions. The Brochure explains that *each of the seven base quantities used in the SI is regarded as having its own dimension*, and goes on to say that *All other quantities [other than base quantities], with the exception of counts, are derived quantities, which may be written in terms of base quantities according to the equations of physics.*

Familiar dimensional expressions, like LT^{-1} , for speed, or MLT^{-2} , for force, can be used to generate compound unit names systematically. Base dimension terms in dimensional expressions are simply replaced with the corresponding base unit symbol, producing compound symbols like $kg \cdot m \cdot s^{-2}$ for force. The unit is effectively a mnemonic for the dimensional expression.

However, a one-to-many relation may exist between a dimensional expression and different kinds of quantity. As the SI Brochure says, *with certain quantities, preference is given to the use of certain special unit names to facilitate the distinction between different quantities having the same dimension*. That is, special unit names, like radian, joule, and so on, help address the problem of SI unit names and symbols that are ambiguous in terms of quantity.

So, the utility of unit-system dimensions for representation of quantities is questionable. In particular, we note that dimensional expressions do not define other dimensions (classes of similar scales for particular kinds of quantity). As pointed out by Emerson [2005],

To say that two quantities are of the same dimension implies a relationship that has significance when in fact it has none.

In spite of this, many digital unit representation systems give prominence to data structures that are closely related to dimensional expressions.

2.4 Unit arithmetic

It is sometimes assumed that unit arithmetic is an inherent property of unit systems. The rules of unit arithmetic are based on quantity calculus, but those for arithmetic are more restrictive.

When arithmetic expressions include units, the terms for units would be interpreted as referring to individual quantities. However, the sameness of unit names does not guarantee the sameness of quantity kinds, as already explained. For example, adding a torque to an energy does not make physical sense but cannot necessarily be detected as an error from the unit symbols (which could be $\text{N} \cdot \text{m}$, or $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$). Furthermore, the unit resulting from a product or quotient of other units cannot be associated with a quantity kind without knowledge of the physics involved. Emerson [2008] has discussed this problem in detail. Finally, although terms of the same quantity kind can be added and subtracted, unit arithmetic further restricts addition and subtraction to expressions in terms of the same units. It makes no sense, for example, to add an inch to a centimetre, although both are units of length.

2.5 Final remarks

For the various reasons presented above, a logical model that represents units of measurement and quantities is hard to find. The familiar conceptual model of a quantity associated with a unit name does not correspond to the semantics of the notation and there is no official guidance regarding how to deal with this difficulty.

That this has not led to major problems when data is exchanged between people is due to skill and, above all, to experience. Ambiguity can usually be resolved by knowing about the context in which data is used. Occasionally difficulties will arise—some of these were mentioned at the 2021 workshop on *The SI in FAIR Digital Data*. However, people can usually recognise a problem and take some appropriate evasive action (again relying on context, skill, and experience).

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